

Design and Emotion Education:

Introducing undergraduate students to emerging design research

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Abstract: This paper investigates the construct of product experience and attachment, with the view to how the research literature, and supporting design strategies, can be introduced to design students at an undergraduate level. The paper proposes that exposing students to the relevance and application of emerging design research in this area, will encourage them to design more sustainable and more emotionally engaging human centered design solutions. Furthermore, it will prepare them for the challenges, which they may face as practicing designers. Issues such as personality, memories, pleasure, longevity and sensory design are explored via three student projects: an investigative study relating to product attachment; a workshop to explore products with personality, and; finally a design challenge to consider interaction and touch.

Key words: *Product attachment, personality, experience, narrative, pleasure.*

1. Introduction

An increasingly competitive consumer market has reinforced the importance that product designers should understand how people experience and interact with the products they design. Designers should seek to understand, how and why, people form relationships with products. With this knowledge, designers could influence a richer and more sustainable connection between the products they design and their users. It is therefore important that design students are introduced to emerging design research, in order to investigate these salient themes so that they may begin to understand the relevance and application of research findings within their discipline. The three student projects, described within this paper, were introduced via a 12-week module entitled ‘Design and the User’. The aim of the module was to encourage students to consider a holistic view of physical, sensory and cognitive human capability. The projects focus on product attachment, products with personality, and sensory design. Each of the projects is underpinned by emerging design research within the area of ‘Emotional Design’ and in addition to exploring these important concepts; they also provided a platform to introduce the relevance and application of design research.

1.1. Overview of projects

The first project that will be presented, describes an investigative study relating to product attachment. In this project, students carried out a research and analysis project which focused on products that were rich in memories, improved with time, provided pleasure and were expressions of self. These items included, favourite childhood toy, a tattoo, a pleasurable product, and a product that they believe improves with time.

The second project described, involved the students taking part in a short workshop to investigate product personality. In this workshop, the students explored the self-congruity theory which suggests that people select to purchase and use goods and services that are consistent with their own self-concept, including the ideal self (the person you would like to be), the public self (the image you think other people have of you) and the real self (what you really think about yourself) [1].

The third and final project to be discussed relates to sensory design and more specifically to product experience and the ‘surprise’ emotion. This project involved the students undertaking the design of a product that had visual-tactual incongruities in order to explore Ludden’s hypothesis that communicating incongruent sensory messages and evoking an emotion of surprise can positively influence the user experience. [2]

Thirty-five 2nd year undergraduate design students took part in the module; 21 male and 14 female.

2. Emotion as a design strategy

Considering emotion as part of a design strategy, presents two very exciting opportunities for designers. Firstly, the increasingly competitive marketplace has resulted in organizations no longer being able to compete on price, quality and technology alone [3]. Consumers are demanding additional differentiators and so organizations are now challenging designers to create enhanced product–user experiences and to design products that emotionally connect with the user. This is evident from recent design strategies adopted by large design-led organizations, such as Peugeot, Samsung and BMW. This year, in order to mark their 200th anniversary, Peugeot rebranded. In addition to evolving their famous lion identity they also introduced a strap line “MOTION & EMOTION” [4], to emphasize their commitment to designing more emotionally engaging products. Figure 1 shows the evolved brand identity together with the new strap line.

Figure 1. Peugeot re-brand to exemplify the adoption of emotion as a design strategy

Samsung electronics president, Mr. Boo-Yoon, announced in his keynote speech at the IFA in September 2009, that their goal was to enhance the emotional relevance and user experience delivered by their products. He said, “For digital products to be loved by consumers, they must inspire the human heart.” [5].

BMW have also assumed an emotionally led design strategy position and are currently promoting the emotion of ‘Joy’ to be synonymous with their cars. A quote from their current website states, “We don’t just build cars. We are the creators of emotion.” [6]. In addition to this they also publish a BMW customer magazine in Germany entitled “Emotion” [8]. Figure 2 shows the front cover of the 4/2009 edition of this publication. A design strategy that focuses on strengthening the emotional bond between product and user, by encouraging product attachment offers the potential for richer emotional experiences and may provide both competitive advantage and product loyalty.

Figure 2. Front cover of 4/2009 edition of BMW Emotion

Secondly, from a sustainability position, the construct of product attachment presents a very important and exciting opportunity. If users are prolonging the life of their products, by taking better care of them and repairing them when they break, then fewer products will end up as landfill. Furthermore, the environmental burden of manufacturing replacement products will be reduced. Encouraging prolonged product use via product attachment, therefore, presents itself as an innovative eco-design strategy, which may offer more sustainable benefits than symptom focused strategies such as design for recycling.

3. Product attachment

Product attachment relates to the emotional bond that users can have with their products and how this bond can influence user behaviour. For example, if a user forms a strong connection with a product, they may handle it with more care, mend it if it breaks, and keep it and use it for a longer period of time [8]. Conversely, if a user feels no emotional bond with a product then they are likely to discard it more quickly; for example, if it breaks or if they become bored of it.

Product attachment can occur at two levels, as a result of certain product variants or specific product specimens [9]. Being attached to certain product variants means that the user is attached to the physical form and/or the function that the product offers. The attachment is somewhat superficial as the same level of attachment could be felt for a similar product of the same type. For example, a user may become attached to a table lamp. They may become attached because they find it easy to use and because it complements the décor of their interior. If the table lamp were to break and be replaced by the same or similar model, the user is unlikely to feel any emotional loss. This is because the user is attached to the product variants and not the specific product specimen.

The second level of product attachment is much deeper and can result in the object becoming irreplaceable. Thus, the same level of attachment could never be felt for a similar product of the same type. For example, a user may become attached to a pocket watch. The user may become attached to the watch because of memories and shared experiences with it; for example, they may have used it at an important time in their life or a close relative could have given it to them. The user may take care of it and repair it if it becomes damaged. It is unlikely that the user would feel the same level of attachment to an exact replica, or to a brand new version of this watch.

The two levels of attachment are not exclusive and a user could experience attachment at both levels. Essentially, this could result in a much stronger product attachment. For example, a user could be attached to their digital camera at both levels. The user could be attached to the physical form of the product, benefit from the function it provides and enjoy the user interface. This level of attachment relates solely to the product variants. If the user were to lose their camera and replace it with the exact same model then the same level of attachment could exist. It is, however, possible for the user to also become attached to a specific camera, so that it would become

irreplaceable. This may occur if the user had embedded personal meaning into the camera, for example they may have a number of personal photos stored on it, or it may have been the first camera they ever owned or it could have been given to them by a loved one.

3.1. Project One: Product Attachment Investigative study

The methodology for the product attachment project was based on a study conducted by Lacey [10], which investigated the reasons why people become attached to drinking cups. Lacey explored the relationship people had with their favourite cups using Norman's three levels of cognitive processing: visceral processing (how something appears); behavioural processing (how something works or feels), and; reflective processing (what something means) [11]. The students were asked to replicate Lacey's study, but rather than exploring why people become attached to cups, they were asked to investigate: their favourite childhood toy; a product that provided pleasure; a product that improved with time, and; a tattoo. These items provided the students with the opportunity to explore a number of different research theories surrounding product attachment. The students were asked, where appropriate, to photograph their items and bring the photographs to class to support discussion.

3.2 Project results

3.2.1 Favourite childhood toy

Students were asked to identify and reflect on their favourite childhood toys in order to explore the product narrative theory. The work of Chapman [12] was used to introduce the theory. Chapman, in his book *Emotionally Durable Design*, credits the product consumer relationship to the product narrative. The more emotional investment a user gives a product the richer the product narrative becomes. Chapman uses the example of a teddy bear to exemplify the narrative phenomena as all over the world teddy bears are cherished by children and the attachment often continues into adult life, long after all other childhood possessions have been discarded. Chapman discusses product attachment as a strategy for sustainable design and proposes that designers should design products that users can emotionally invest in.

The majority of students reported that their favourite childhood toy was a stuffed toy or a baby doll. The remaining students preferred cars, building blocks, games and other toys. Of the students whose favourite toy was a soft toy or a baby doll, almost all of them still have, and still cherish it. This was not the case with the students reporting other toys, with only a very small percentage of them still possessing their toy.

In most cases the soft toys and baby dolls had great sentimental value to the students, often being given to them at an early age by a close relative. The owners of these toys had many stories about them and in some cases the toys had been on very emotional journeys with their owners. In the case of the soft toys, the attachment was further enhanced by the great sensory pleasure, that the toy gave to the students e.g. many students discussed the softness or the smell of the material. This suggested that multi-sensory elements may play an important role in product attachment. An example of one of the student's favourite childhood toy and the rationale as related to Norman's model of cognitive processing can be seen in Table 1. The toy was a teddy bear given to him by his father who has since passed away. The example describes visceral, behavioural and reflective benefits offered by the toy, however, it is the reflective benefits that relate most strongly to why the user has become so attached. This was true for the majority of the students who demonstrated a strong attachment.

Toy	Visceral	Behavioural	Reflective
	He has white ears, hands and feet. Some of the threads from the stitching on the nose have come loose which now appear as a moustache which I think gives him more character.	He is nice and soft and cuddly	My Dad gave him to me when I was born. My Dad has since passed away so it means a lot to me.

Table 1. Example of one student's results from the "favourite childhood toy" analysis

3.2.2. A product that provides pleasure

Students explored how a product can provide their user with pleasure and the impact this can have on product attachment by investigating pleasurable products. The pleasure paradigm, as described by Jordan [13], was presented as a means to categorise the source of pleasure: physical (achieved via human senses); social (resulting from relationships with others); psychological (concerning cognitive and emotional reactions), and; ideological (relating to peoples values). The students then attempted to map the four pleasure categories onto Normans reflective, behavioural and visceral cognitive processing model. The importance of pleasure in establishing product attachment was introduced by research carried out by Schifferstein et al [14] who found that pleasure experienced through product 'use' enhanced product attachment. The students used this hypothesis to investigate whether the products they identified provided pleasure through product 'use' or otherwise.

In almost all of the cases investigated, the students found that the act of using the product was integral to the experience of pleasure. This substantiated the findings of Schifferstein. Furthermore, when the students mapped the items categorized in terms of the pleasure paradigm onto Normans model, they found that behavioural processing attributed most frequently to the experiences of pleasure. Figure 3 shows some examples of the products that were selected because they give their owner pleasure. The products have been categorized using Jorman's pleasure paradigm; ideological, psychological, social and physical.

Figure 3. Products which provide pleasure categorized using Jordan's pleasure paradigm

3.2.3 A product that was perceived to improve with time

Students investigated the role of memories and if products can actually improve with use, by identifying a product that is perceived to improve with time. Schifferstein [14], as well as advocating the importance of pleasure in establishing product attachment, also recognized the significance of memories. His study, which

focused on clocks, lamps and ornaments, concluded that in the case of new products, enjoyment was the most influential factor and in the case of older products it was memories that had the strongest influence. Students were asked to consider if the product had improved as a result of emotional investment and memories or whether the function had actually improved with repeated use, which would support new proposed design strategies [15] to intentionally design objects so that the function improves with repeated use.

In the cases where the students assigned a functional improvement over time, it was predominantly as a result of a change in the material properties, for example the material became softer; a pair of boxing gloves, a pillow and a leather jacket. There were, however, examples of perceived functional improvement, which resulted from the users improved competence with the product. For example, a guitar was reported to have functionally improved as the player improved. The guitar may not have actually functionally improved but because the player had improved the guitar sounded better; the product and user were perceived to develop and improve together. Another interesting example was a car. The student who claimed his car improved with time had completely personalized it and although it constantly caused him mechanical trouble he loved everything about it. This example is interesting for two reasons. Firstly, the student felt that the car improved more and more each time he personalized some aspect of it and secondly he felt that the function of the car had improved as a result of his enhanced mechanical capability. He was becoming more mechanically astute each time he encountered a problem with the car and as a result the car was performing better. This example also demonstrates a shared development journey for the product and the user. Figure 4 shows some examples of the products selected by the students that they felt improved with time.

Figure 4. Examples of products which the students felt improved with time

3.2.4. Tattoo

In order to investigate Csikszentmihallyi and Halton's theory [16], that material possessions are symbols of self, the students were asked to investigate the ultimate symbol of self – a tattoo. Csikszentmihallyi and Halton's view of product attachment is that material possessions are symbols of where we have been, who we are now and what we aspire to be. They describe the relationship that people have with products as a self-development process and material objects as an extension of self. Their theory extends to include how product attachments are related to key self-development processes; expressing individualism and integration with others.

For this part of the project, all of the students interviewed a friend or a family member who had a tattoo. They were required to find out what the tattoo symbolised, how long they have had it, if they feel differently about it now than when they first got it and any other relevant information.

Only one of the students reported that their interviewee felt any regret. Most students reported that their interviewee felt much stronger about their tattoo now, than when they first got it. The majority of responses as to what the tattoo meant to the owner were very personal and often related to aspects of their personality, or an

important time in their lives. The example shown in Figure 5 demonstrates a very rich personal narrative. The top half of the tattoo, which includes cogs and mechanics, represents the interviewee's career as a design engineer. The girl symbolizes how content she is with herself and her career. As you go down the tattoo, the imagery symbolizes the more feminine and flighty side of her personality. The last quarter represents the more mischievous sensual and darker side of her personality. Mixed throughout the tattoo are other different symbols, for example, the fish represents her star sign and the jewels represents her love of shiny things. The tattoo was designed by the interviewee, which offered even deeper personalization and emotional investment. It is anticipated that she will continue to add to this tattoo as her life develops and takes new directions.

Figure 5. An example of one of the tattoos that was investigated

3.3 Product attachment project conclusions

For many of the students, this project was their first exposure to academic research and their first practical experience of conducting design related research. As the project involved the students reflecting on their own attachments and those of their friends and family, they all quickly engaged with, and enjoyed the project. Many of them reported that they had never considered the importance of why they preferred one product to another or why they kept certain products and discarded others. The realization that they could potentially influence the level of attachment that a user could feel for a product was extremely valuable for their development as a designer.

The students proposed that allowing users to personalize a product or adapt it in some way in order to express themselves could provide enhanced opportunity for product attachment. They also recognized the role of material selection if they wanted their products to improve with time and the importance of considering how memories can be associated with a product and how pleasure could be introduced.

4. Product personality

Product personality relates to a collection of personality traits that people use to describe specific products and to differentiate others. [17] One organization that is renowned for their use of product personality as a design strategy is the Italian kitchenware company, Alessi. Alessi's products are often given human names and adopt human or animal characteristics and personality traits which make them endearing to the consumer. Examples of

products produced by Alessi that embody personalities are shown in figure 6. The examples shown could be described using personality characteristics such as cute or friendly.

Figure 6. Anna G Corkscrew, Cisco eggcup, Tigrito cat bowl and Don Banana kitchen box

Govers research suggests that products, which embody personalities that reflect the self-concept of their owner positively, influence consumer preference and can encourage stronger product attachment [18]. This theory, known as the self-congruity theory, has presented an interesting design strategy; embedding a personality into a product that is congruent with the target user could enhance product attachment.

4. 1 Project Two: Product personality workshop

It is easier to assign personality traits to people than it is to assign them to products. In reality, people frequently stereotype what personalities other people have based solely on their appearance. This assessment can influence everyday decisions that we make, such as, who to stop and ask directions from or who to sit next to on a train. Our assessments are often largely based on facial features, hairstyle, and clothing etc [19]. As the students were more familiar with assigning personality traits to people than to products, the workshop focused on encouraging them to consider personality traits in terms of how they might stereotype people (e.g. facial features, hairstyle and clothing) and then attempt to translate these characteristics into design features of a product.

The workshop began by first asking the students to create a superhero. They had to give their superhero special powers, a costume and any necessary accessories. This was merely a quick creative session to open the student's minds to developing exaggerated personas. They were then given a template, which contained the outline of a face and some questions. They were asked to create a visual representation of a stereotypical character based on a personality trait, which they were assigned (the assigned personality trait was given on the template). The personality traits assigned were, reliable, aggressive, lively and quiet. The traits were selected from Eysenck's personality dimensions model to represent the two main personality dimensions known as introversion-extraversion and emotionality-stability [20]. They were required to give their characters facial features, clothing, accessories and a hairstyle. They were also required to answer a number of questions about their character, and their characters lifestyle. The questions related to: their name; age; residence; occupation; hobbies; music preferences; ambitions; clothes, and; how they move. This information provided a rich narrative of who their character really was and provided the students with rich information on which to base their characters physical appearance on.

Subsequent to creating their character, the students were tasked to design a kitchenware product that they felt embodied the personality of their character. In addition to embodying the personality of their character, they also had to consider the self congruity theory and attempt to design a product that their character would be positively influenced to buy.

Figure 7 shows an example of a character created by one of the students who had been assigned the personality

trait 'aggressive'. The character is called Willie, he is 26 and he works as a builder's laborer. He lives in a council estate in Glasgow and spends his time drinking and fighting. He enjoys rave music and mostly wears braces and string vests. He walks fast but with a heavy swagger. The student designed a cup to embody the personality of Willie and also appeal to him. The cup is in the form of a clenched fist to represent Willie's aggressive behaviour and love of fighting. As Willie works on a building site, he has a number of tea breaks throughout the day. The masculine form of Willie's cup shows everybody that although he is only drinking tea, he is still very tough.

Figure 7. Example of the character Willie and the 'Willie range' cup

4.1 Product personality workshop conclusions

The products with personality workshop provided the students the opportunity to explore the self-congruity theory in a gentle and humorous way. Although only a short workshop, it did introduce the concept that products with personality could be seen as a new approach to human factors where objects are considered to have relationships with people as opposed to just tools with which people use to complete tasks. [13] By providing such limited information to base their characters on, students had to use their creative skills to really animate their character, often through humour and exaggerated stereotypes. As a result the students created very interesting characters, which were rich in personality and provided a useful basis on which to inform their designs. Describing the characters in detail through answering the questions provided greater opportunity to replicate human characteristics or behaviour in the design of their products. Interestingly, the students who had extraverted personality traits (aggressive and lively) found the exercise easier, than those who had introverted traits (reliable and quiet), and in most cases produced more interesting concepts. The students proposed that attempting to design products with extraverted personalities could produce more desirable products.

5.0 Sensory design

People experience different products using different senses, for example; one can see, hear and touch a telephone. Previous research suggests that stimulating multiple senses can enhance product experience [21]. Design strategies, which focus on multisensory experiences are not uncommon, for example; A car manufacturer may consider the way a car looks, the sound the door makes when it closes, the sound of the engine revving and, the smell and touch of the interior. Engaging all of these senses (sight,

touch, smell and sound) helps them to convey a consistent message and an enhanced product experience. Conversely to this, research conducted by Ludden [2] proposes that if an incongruent message is communicated then an emotion of surprise could be experienced. Ludden also suggests that surprising products are often more interesting for the user to interact with and can lead to increased product recognition.

5.1 Project Three: Sensory design

The sensory design project related specifically to investigating Luddens hypothesis that products communicating incongruent messages evoke the emotion of surprise and lead to enhanced user experience. The students were asked to explore the concept of ‘surprise’ by designing a product that had visual-tactual incongruities. The students were shown a number of example products before commencing the project to ensure that they understood the concept of incongruity between what an object looks like and how it feels to touch. Figure 8 shows one of the examples shown to the students: Felt stone cushions designed by Ronel Jordann [22]. The colour and tone of the soft felt wool, together with additional embellishments, imitates the natural marbling design often found in real stones. Although the cushions look hard, like stone, they are in fact soft.

Figure 8. Felt stone cushions by Ronel Jordaan

One of the students response to the design challenge was to design a metal coat stand that looked like it was a balloon tied to a piece of string. Under normal circumstances you would not be able to hang the weight of a coat on a string tied to a balloon thus the student was successful in achieving an incongruity between how their product looked and how it performed when interacted with it. The student realised this concept by manipulating a steel rod into the form of a rope arbitrarily lying on the ground. The rod then formed a vertical section, which led to a loop where the balloon would be attached. Fixed to the rod were two discreet hooks on which to hang coats. The rod was covered in a fabric cable sleeve to give the effect of rope. A sketch of this design concept can be seen in figure 9.

Figure 9. Balloon coat stand by Lucy Ross (2nd year design student)

5.2 Sensory design project conclusions

The sensory design project was very different to the design challenges that the students usually face. At the beginning of the project they found it difficult understand the concept of visual- tactual incongruity, often confusing it with visual – visual incongruity. They also found it difficult to appreciate the value of creating incongruent messages and the majority of early concepts looked like they might disappoint the user and degraded the product experience as opposed to enhance it. In order to progress the project, a short sensory exercise was introduced to encourage the students to consider their sense of touch. The students were blindfolded and then given a selection of tactile objects to touch. They were asked to feel the objects, guess what the object was, what it looked like and what colour it was. Based on their perception of what the object was for and what it looked like, the students were then asked to imagine different uses for the product by focusing on contradictory properties. For example, imagining a feather as a table leg. A discussion following the design challenge, revealed that the students felt more aware of how the different sense modalities could be stimulated through design and how focusing on this could create interesting products. However, it was also discussed that once the surprise has been revealed to the user the product could become boring.

6.0 Concluding remarks

Product designers are being increasingly challenged to design products that users can emotionally connect with. It is therefore critical that design education prepares students for this challenge by exposing them to emerging design research addressing the salient themes of emotional product experience. The three projects described within this paper afforded the students the opportunity to explore these themes within a realistic and practical context. Underpinning the projects with emerging design research was important as it allowed the students to compare their own findings with those of esteemed researchers. This provided validity to their findings in addition to encouraging them to consider the relevance and application of design research.

7.0 References

- [1] Sirgy, M. J. (1982) Self-concept on consumer behaviour: a critical review. *Journal of consumer research*, 9 (3) pp 287-300
- [2] Ludden. G.D.S., Schifferstein H.N.J., Hekkert P. Visual-tactual incongruities in products as sources of surprise. *Empirical Studies of the Arts*, 2009, 27(1) 61-87
- [3] Thackara, J. *Winners! How successful companies innovate by Design*. 1997 (Gower publishing Ltd)

- [4] Peugeot website, Available at <http://www.peugeot.co.uk>. [Accessed 10th March 2010]
- [5] Samsung website, Available at http://www.samsung.com/us/news/newsRead.do?news_seq=14517&page=1 [Accessed 8th March 2010]
- [6] BMW website, Available at http://www.bmw.com/com/en/insights/technology/joy/bmw_joy.html [Accessed 8th March 2010]
- [7] BMW Emotion, Available at <http://www.heller-partner.de/en/branchen/index.php?kampagne=100486> [Accessed 8th March 2010]
- [8] Mugge R., Schoormans, J.P.L. and Schifferstein, H.N.J. Design Strategies to postpone consumers' product replacement: The value of a strong person-product relationship. *The design Journal*, 2005, 8(2), 38-48.
- [9] Mugge R., Schoormans, J.P.L. and Schifferstein, H.N.J. (2008) Product attachment: Design strategies to stimulate the emotional bonding to products. H. Schifferstein & P. Hekkert, (Eds.), *Product Experience* (pp 427 - 428). Elsevier Science
- [10] Lacey M. Contemporary ceramic design for meaningful interaction and emotional durability: A case study. *International Journal of Design*, 2009, 3(2), 87-92
- [11] Norman, D.A. *Emotional Design*. 2005 (New York: Basic books).
- [12] Chapman, J. *Emotionally durable design*. 2005 (Trowbridge UK: Cromwell press)
- [13] Jordan P.W. *Designing pleasurable products, an introduction to the new human factors*. 2000 (London: Taylor & Francis)
- [14] Schifferstein, H.N.J, Mugge R. & Hekkert P. Designing consumer product attachment. In *Design and Emotion: The experience of everyday things*, pp. 327-331, 1999 (Taylor & Francis)
- [15] Helms M., Leifer L. Designing objects that improve with use. (2009) *Proceedings of the International conference on Engineering Design, ICED'09*, (pp 7-311 – 7-320) Stanford
- [16] Csikszentmihalyi M. & Halton E. *The meaning of things: Domestic symbols of the self*, 2008 (Cambridge University Press)
- [17] Govers, P.C.M., & Mugge, R. (2004) "I love my Jeep because its tough like me". *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Design and Emotion*. Turkey.
- [18] Govers, P.C.M. Product personality and its influence on consumer preference. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 2005, 22(4) 189-197
- [19] Desmet P.M.A. Product personality in physical interaction. *Design Studies*, 2008, 29 458-477
- [20] Bernstein D.A & Nash P.W. (2008) *Essentials of Psychology*. Houghton Mifflin (pp 429-430)
- [21] Schifferstein, H. N. J. Spence C (2008). Multisensory product experience. In H. Schifferstein & P. Hekkert, (Eds.), *Product Experience* (pp. 133-134). Elsevier Science.
- [22] Ronel Jordaan website, Available at <http://www.roneljordan.com> [Accessed 8th March 2010]